

Investigation of the Relationship Between Architectural Design Properties of Monumental Masjids and Energy Efficiency: The Case of Konya

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Abstract

Monumental religious buildings are valuable elements of cultural and architectural heritage, and documenting the architectural design properties of these buildings is of great importance. At the same time, the climate-related design properties of monumental mosques or masjids characterized by unique work plans are important in terms of providing energy-efficient comfort conditions in the interior. In this respect, this study handles monumental masjids built in Konya during the Anatolian Seljuk Period. It is aimed to create and document the inventory of monumental religious buildings and to investigate the relationship between the design properties of these buildings and energy efficiency. In the study prepared within the scope of the scientific research project (BAP), the Bulgur Tekke Masjid built during the Anatolian Seljuk Period is examined. The religious building, whose architectural design properties are determined, is modeled using the DesignBuilder simulation software and analyzed in terms of energy efficiency. The findings show that monumental religious buildings have great importance in terms of energy efficiency in line with their architectural design properties. Studies conducted in this field are limited, and this study is pioneering in this respect.

Keywords: Monumental masjids, Anatolian Seljuk Period, energy efficiency.

Anıtsal Mescitlerin Mimari Tasarım Özellikleri ile Enerji Verimliliği Arasındaki İlişkinin Araştırılması: Konya Örneği

Öz

Anıtsal dini yapılar kültürel ve mimari mirasının değerli öğeleridir ve bu yapıların mimari tasarım özelliklerinin belgelenmesi büyük bir öneme sahiptir. Aynı zamanda, benzersiz çalışma planlarıyla karakterize edilen anıtsal cami veya mescitlerin iklime bağlı tasarım özellikleri iç mekanda konfor koşullarının enerji verimli bir şekilde sağlanması açısından önemlidir. Bu açıdan bu çalışmada, Konya'da Anadolu Selçuklu Döneminde inşa edilen anıtsal mescitler ele alınmaktadır. Anıtsal dini yapıların envanterinin oluşturularak belgelenmesi ve bu yapıların tasarım özellikleri ile enerji verimliliği arasındaki ilişkinin araştırılması hedeflenmektedir. Bilimsel araştırma projesi kapsamında (BAP) hazırlanan çalışmada, Anadolu Selçuklu Döneminde inşa edilen Bulgur Tekke Mescidi ele alınmaktadır. Mimari tasarım özellikleri belirlenen dini yapı DesignBuilder simülasyon programı aracılığıyla modellenerek, enerji verimliliği açısından analiz edilmektedir. Elde edilen bulgular anıtsal dini yapıların mimari tasarım özellikleri doğrultusunda enerji verimliliği açısından büyük bir değere sahip olduğunu göstermektedir. Bu alanda yapılan çalışmalar sınırlıdır ve bu açıdan bu çalışma öncü niteliktedir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Anıtsal mescitler, Anadolu Selçuklu Dönemi, enerji verimliliği.

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1. Introduction

The urban structure is formed and constantly developed over time, but in addition to this development, it remains the same in the consciousness of the societies. Konya, one of the important examples of this situation, has great importance in terms of its location on the Silk Road in Anatolia and its place in the historical process. Konya, one of the oldest settlements in Anatolia, has been home to various civilizations (Yenice, 2012). Konya has been one of the most important Turkish-Islamic cultural and art centers of Anatolia throughout its history. The city was the capital of the Anatolian Seljuk Civilization and one of the important state centers of the Ottoman Empire, and has preserved its importance for many years. It has been an architectural center throughout history and has precious elements of cultural and architectural heritage. Mosques and masjids built during the Seljuk and Ottoman Periods provide the foundation for the urban morphology of our civilization, creating a distinctive typology through their plan, section, and facade properties. This architectural heritage needs to be protected and documented.

Mosques and masjids, which are precious elements of architectural and cultural heritage, represent the central space where people come together for their weekly and daily prayers and are considered social, educational, and cultural spaces for Muslims' activities. Mosques and masjids are characterized by having a unique intermittent working plan compared to other building types. They are used simultaneously in a specific region and time (Azmi & Kandar, 2019). In this case, the periods when the building needs to be heated and cooled affect the energy demand in line with the climatic zones (Al-Homoud et al., 2005). The mosques or masjids' climate-related design properties affect the building thermal performance and the indoor comfort conditions (Abdou et al., 2005). Therefore, the thermal comfort of mosques or masjids largely depends on the integrated and total thermal performance of the building components, such as roofs, walls, and windows, working together as a system (Al-Homoud et al., 2009). A mosque with poor thermal performance consumes more energy to provide comfort conditions. In this respect, the heating and cooling load of the mosque is quite important, especially in terms of energy efficiency.

In a study conducted to determine the factors affecting energy efficiency in mosque buildings (Azmi et al., 2021), contemporary literature on energy use in mosques was reviewed. As a result of the study, it was stated that the building envelope design (thermal design) and climatic factors are the most important factors in the energy use of mosques. In the study conducted by Al-Homoud et al., the indoor comfort conditions and the relationship between these conditions and the energy consumption levels were evaluated for three mosques located in the hot humid climate zone of Damman, Saudi Arabia. It was stated that only one of the mosques examined had a thermal insulation layer on its envelope. The two mosques without insulation reported higher energy consumption and dissatisfaction in terms of thermal comfort. As a result, the importance of integrating a thermal insulation layer was emphasized (Al-Homoud et al., 2009). Various studies show that older buildings have lower energy demands in line with their compact urban layout and the material use with thermal mass convenient for climatic conditions (Azmi et al., 2021).

This study, prepared within the scope of a scientific research project, aims to create and document the inventory of a monumental religious structure built in the Anatolian Seljuk Period in Konya, to contribute to studies on energy efficiency and monumental religious buildings, to show the value and importance of these buildings in terms of energy efficiency by analyzing the current energy demands of masjids, which are important elements of the monumental architectural heritage built centuries ago. There is not enough research in the literature on the basic design properties and energy performances of masjids. In this respect, this study is a pioneer for future studies. At the same time, it is aimed that the relationship between the design criteria and construction techniques of monumental masjids and energy efficiency will inspire and guide designers in the design of religious buildings with a sense of sacred worship.

2. Material and Method

This paper is prepared for the Scientific Research Project (BAP) scope. Among the monumental religious buildings investigated within the scope of this project, the Bulgur Tekke (13th century) Masjid, built in Konya during the Anatolian Seljuk Period, is handled in this study. Developments during the Seljuk period shaped Konya's historical architecture. The Seljuk cities' smallest unit is the neighborhood, and the neighborhood's basic unit is usually the masjids that gives its name to the neighborhood. Mosques are important social centers where Muslims come together. The construction of the palace and grand mosque during the Ottoman period developed the historical focus point of the city around an administrative and religious centre.

First of all, information about the Konya and the masjid belonging to the Anatolian Seljuk Civilization are collected in the light of the literature. The masjid is visualized with the drone, and its properties are documented with photographs. The drawings of the masjid in the electronic environment are taken from the Konya Regional Directorate of Foundations, and the drawings are colored, and the current situation based on on-site determinations and its relationship with its immediate surroundings are processed on the drawings. In line with the literature review, visuals, on-site determinations and drawings, plan section, facade, and top cover elements are explained, as well as construction techniques and material properties. The masjid's architectural design properties are documented, and the masjid is modeled in the Design-Builder simulation software. In the DesignBuilder simulation program, models specific to masjid buildings with characteristic features are developed, taking into account the worshippers, usage times, and occupancy rate. In line with the simulation results and findings, the evaluations are explained.

3. Findings and Discussion

In this section, first of all, Bulgur Tekke Masjid's architectural design properties are explained. This masjid is also analyzed in terms of energy efficiency.

3.1. Bulgur Tekke Masjid's Architectural Design Properties

The construction of the Bulgur Tekke Masjid dates back to the second half of the 13th century. The masjid was built in Konya in the Anatolian Seljuk period and was built using a masonry technique. Bulgur Tekke Masjid's form is square, and the masjid's plan layout is three spaces. The masjid's top cover property is a dome. The religious building order is attached. The masjid's height (h) is 9.80 m and the total area is 181.83 m². In Figure 1, Bulgur Tekke Masjid's front view and plan are shown.

Figure 1. Bulgur Tekke Masjid front view and plan (Photograph and image by the authors, 2019)

In terms of material properties and construction techniques, stone and brick were used together in the Bulgur Tekke Masjid's walls, the mosque's wall thickness is 120 cm, and the bond technique is

masonry. The stone up to the mantel base level, and brick after this level. In terms of openings, window ratios are mixed. The Masjid has a dome, and the mosque's top cover technique is masonry. The dome's material is brick, the dome's diameter is 703 cm, and the dome's thickness is 42 cm. There are no openings on the top cover. The masjid's flooring material is wood, and the last prayer hall flooring is stone. The masjid has a minaret. In Figure 2 Bulgur Tekke Masjid's A-A Section is shown and in Figure 3 Bulgur Tekke Masjid's elevation is shown.

Figure 2. Bulgur Tekke Masjid's A-A section (Authors, 2019)

Figure 3. Bulgur Tekke Masjid's north elevation (Authors, 2019)

3.2. The Bulgur Tekke Masjid in the scope of Energy Efficiency

The Bulgur Tekke Masjid, belonging to the Anatolian Seljuk Period, is analyzed in terms of energy efficiency in light of the architectural design properties and simulation results. The masjid is modeled and analyzed using Design Builder software. Design Builder is an EnergyPlus-based simulation software tool developed to measure and control the building design performance in terms of energy, comfort, carbon, and lighting (Zhang, 2014).

Konya is located in Türkiye's temperate-dry climate zone, a climate zone where heating periods are important. Design parameters affecting the energy performance of a building are handled as the building location, the building orientation, the distance between other buildings, the building form, the building envelope's optical and thermophysical properties, solar control, and natural ventilation layout (Lechner, 2015). It can be stated that energy-efficient design parameters are also valid for a mosque and a masjid building. However, mosque buildings have elements that direct their basic designs, such as the qibla, the qibla wall, the mihrab, and the minbar, and these factors need to be evaluated. The masjid buildings' orientation, in the direction of a characteristic design property, is the qibla direction. The orientation of the Konya mosques and masjids (their qibla), which are handled within the scope of the scientific research project, is in the south direction.

The immediate surroundings of a building, the distance between other buildings, and the building order affect the solar radiation and wind factors. The Bulgur Tekke Masjid's building order is attached. This situation affects the passive benefit or protection of the building from solar and wind effects. In this respect, the building order is one of the parameters that directly affects the building energy load.

Bulgur Tekke Masjid’s form is square, which is desired in the moderate dry climate region. In Table 1 Bulgur Tekke Masjid’s other design properties affecting the energy loads and the heating-cooling and total energy loads per m² are shown, and energy loads are shown, and in Figure 4 Bulgur Tekke Masjid’s Energy Model is shown.

Table 1. Bulgur Tekke Masjid’s architectural design properties and energy loads

Masjid Name		Bulgur Tekke Masjid, 13th Century Anatolian Seljuk Period
Total Area of Masjid m ²		181.83 m ²
Masjid height (h)		9.80 m
Wall Material		Brick
Wall Thickness		120 cm
Top Cover Material		Brick
Top Cover Thickness		42 cm
Window-Wall Ratio (%)	South	8.97
	North	0.00
	East	4.94
	West	0.00
Cooling Load per m ² kWh		20.29
Heating Load per m ² kWh		114.42
Energy Consumed per m ² (heating-cooling-lighting) kWh		141.52

Figure 4. Bulgur Tekke Masjid’s energy model (Authors, 2019)

The Bulgur Tekke Masjid’s annual energy consumption per m² is 141.52 kWh, heating load per m² is 114.42 kWh, and cooling load per m² is 20.29 kWh. It is seen that a large part of the energy consumed is the heating load. In terms of building materials, the walls and dome materials of the masjid are bricks. Brick building materials have the qualification to contribute to the heating and cooling loads of buildings. Thermal conductivity properties of the building envelope’s opaque and transparent components are important factors that can affect the energy demands of the buildings.

The thermal conductivity of the wall varies depending on the properties of the building material and the wall thickness. The type of brick material used for the Bulgur Tekke (13th Century) Masjid, the wall thickness, and the type of glass used in the openings should be considered as factors affecting the thermal conductivity of the envelope and therefore the energy demand of the building. It can be said that the building materials used for the Bulgur Tekke Masjid reduce the energy load of the building. In

this context, the envelope properties should be evaluated as a parameter affecting the energy demand of the mosque or masjid. In Figure 5 Bulgur Tekke Masjid's envelope is shown.

Figure 5. Bulgur Tekke Masjid's envelope (Photograph by the authors, 2019)

The openings in the building envelope depending on the directions directly affect the energy demand of the building in terms of solar radiation gain and beneficial effects of wind. Openings in the south direction provide direct solar radiation gain, especially openings in the north direction are of great importance to benefit from wind effects. In this respect, the opening ratios depending on the directions of Bulgur Tekke Masjid should be evaluated as a parameter affecting the energy loads of the masjid. As a result, the parameters affecting the energy load of a monumental religious building can be evaluated as building materials, especially envelope design, wall thickness, multi-directional openings, top cover properties, thermal conductivity, physical environmental properties such as building order, and characteristic properties. In addition, building volume should be handled and evaluated as an important factor.

4. Conclusion and Suggestions

This study investigates the historical and monumental religious building in Konya, one of the most important centers of Turkish-Islamic art and culture, built in the Anatolian Seljuk Period, in terms of energy efficiency. The relationship between the masjid's architectural design properties and energy efficiency is evaluated. First of all, the monumental masjid's plan, section, envelope properties, construction techniques, and material properties have been documented. The Bulgur Tekke Masjid's energy consumption is analyzed. Creating an inventory of masjids, determining their place in the historical process and current situations, and analyzing them in terms of energy efficiency are of great importance for architectural heritage.

The mosques and masjids examined within the scope of the scientific research project and the Bulgur Tekke Masjid have traditional architectural design properties and construction techniques. The use of materials with thermal mass that are traditional and appropriate for climatic conditions is a sustainable approach that will affect the energy demand of the masjid buildings. It can be said that acceptable results have been obtained in terms of energy efficiency in line with the energy loads consumed per m^2 of the Bulgur Tekke Masjid. The monumental religious buildings analyzed are energy efficient in light of today's energy demands and traditional design properties and construction techniques.

At the same time, it is stated that building volume is an important parameter for religious building types in terms of energy efficiency analyses. The Design Builder simulation software calculates the energy loads per m^2 . It has been determined that for buildings where volume is an important factor, such as monumental mosques and masjids, m^2 type analyses are inadequate, and volume-related (m^3) analysis results are necessary. As a result, positive results are obtained in terms of energy efficiency in the study. Studies in the field of monumental religious buildings and energy efficiency are limited. In

this respect, this study is pioneering and is expected to create potential research scopes for future research. At the same time, it will throw light on designers.

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The article complies with national and international research and publication ethics. Ethics Committee approval was not required for the study.

Author Contribution and Conflict of Interest Disclosure Information

All authors contributed equally to the article. There is no conflict of interest.

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